
AUTHENTIC MATERIAL'S IMPACT ON PROMOTING SPOKEN ENGLISH

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Annotation.

At all levels, using authentic resources is regarded as a crucial part of learning a language. Additionally, it is a well-known fact among specialists that this is a contentious and passionate idea. It examines the history of employing authentic resources and identifies the most advantageous authentic materials for educational purposes. The descriptive research methodology is used in this study because it is most useful for describing the study's topic. The utilization of authentic materials stimulates the learners' attention and motivation, keeping them from becoming disinterested or worn out. The dullness of manufactured writing is lessened with authentic materials. It significantly contributes to achieving a program's learning objective. The findings of this study were also anticipated to show how adding real materials to verbal English expression improves the speaking skills of EFL students. The study's goals are to increase secondary school students' speaking abilities, inspire them to learn the language, and increase their understanding of the value of real resources such as newspaper articles, weather forecasts, horoscopes, etc.

Keywords.

authenticity, speaking skills, enhancing speaking skills, context, the importance of authentic materials.

Introduction.

The primary goal of language learning is to improve speaking ability because the current study is interested in describing the significance and potency of authentic materials in increasing spoken English language skills. According to Nunan, the success of language learning is determined by one's capacity to carry on a conversation in the (target) language. It means that speaking is a sign of language mastery, which is regarded as success in learning a second language. Learners who have developed these skills in their first language are likely to find it easier to pick up these skills in other languages. According to the requirements of the various

groups of learners, teachers implement various pedagogical techniques and teaching methods, such as behavioral, cognitive, and communicative, during various activities. They encourage students to use and have access to real resources like cable and satellite TV, radio, readily available books, and periodicals that expose them to and aid in the mastery of authentic language⁴⁵.

Nunan defined authentic materials as spoken or written language data that has been generated during genuine communication and not material that has been developed intentionally for language teaching objectives. Numerous authors claim that there are resources for real spoken materials that can give teachers and students access to spoken language; one such resource is television (TV). Knowing about this source, numerous educators and academics have employed various TV shows, such as sitcoms, soap operas, and featured films, in their research on successful teaching and learning techniques. Authenticity was initially used to describe any genuine or organic communication situation. According to Kramsch, authentic language refers to the language used in daily life and is not intended for academic objectives. Any "written or spoken texts" that are frequently not meant to be used in language training are referred to as authentic materials or authentic texts. Wallace describes authentic texts similarly, as "real-life text, not written for pedagogical purposes."

These resources are therefore probably not offered or created with teaching English to non-native speakers in mind. Foreign students are originally not offered them. According to Marrow, who was quoted by Yugandha, "a stretch of real language produced by a real speaker or writer for a real audience and designed to carry a real message of some sort" is what constitutes "a real message of some sort."⁴⁶ According to Harmer, authentic texts whether written or spoken are those that are created for native speakers. These are real materials created for the target audience rather than language learners. Nunan believes that any content that has not been created particularly for language training should be considered authentic in this case. These definitions help us understand what authentic materials mean: they are written in real language, made for native speakers, and not for instructional purposes. In this sense, there are many authentic resources in our daily lives, including newspaper and magazine articles, television and radio broadcasts, regular talks, meetings, papers, speeches, and movies⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ Guariento, W. & Morley, J. (2001), Text and task authenticity in the EFL classroom, *ELT Journal* 55(4), 347-353.

⁴⁶ Tomlinson Brian, (1998), *Materials Development in Language Teaching*, Cambridge University Press.

⁴⁷ Hyland Ken. (2003), *Second Language Writing*, Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press.

The Internet is among the most helpful. Newspapers and other materials soon become outdated, but the Internet is constantly updated, more visually appealing, and interactive. In language education, authentic resources are categorized so that they can be used according to the requirements of a certain class. Gebhard suggests that real materials can be divided into three groups. Authentic Listening-Viewing Materials: Radio advertisements, music, documentaries, quiz shows, cartoons, news clips, comedies, movies, soap operas, and TV advertising⁴⁸. Slides, pictures, paintings, drawings by youngsters, stick figures, wordless street signs, silhouettes, magazine images, ink blots, postcard images, wordless picture books, stamps, and X-rays are examples of authentic visual materials.

Newspaper articles, movie trailers, music lyrics, restaurant menus, street signs, cereal boxes, information pamphlets, maps, TV guides, comic books, greeting cards, and bus schedules are examples of authentic text sources. Both the teaching and the learning processes benefit from the use of authentic resources. In terms of the learning process, they offer EFL students a variety of elements like motivation, interaction with genuine language variety, and sufficiency to students' demands. However, they continue to use a creative teaching approach in their lessons. The following are the key benefits of adopting authentic materials, according to Rodgers, T.⁴⁹:

1. They have a positive effect on learner motivation.
2. They provide authentic cultural information.
3. They provide exposure to real language.
4. They relate more closely to learners' needs.
5. They support a more creative approach to teaching.

At the post-intermediate level, it is advised that students use authentic resources because they are expected to have a large and diverse vocabulary in the target language as well as a command of the various sentence construction patterns. At the post-intermediate level, authentic resources can be used in the classroom, according to Guariento & Morley. This may be explained by the fact that most students at this level are proficient in all of the structures and a wide variety of vocabulary in the target language⁵⁰.

⁴⁸ Jordan, R. R (1997), *English for Academic Purposes: A Guide and Resource for Teachers*. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.

⁴⁹ Richards, J. and Rodgers, T. (2001), *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

⁵⁰ Kramsch Claire, (1993), *Context & Culture in Language Teaching*, Oxford University Press.

Pre-intermediate levels are not advised to employ authentic resources since they place an excessive strain on both teachers and students. They could demotivate students who are anticipated to lack language and structural knowledge⁵¹. It may be concluded that authentic resources make learners feel better about engaging in the "real" language as long as teachers give them pedagogical support in order to overcome the challenges that teachers confront while using authentic materials. Here are a variety of options for achieving this:

It is advised to use authentic resources that advance students' comprehension because it keeps them engaged. Songs and other well-known literary authentic materials are also encouraged because they contribute to the relaxed atmosphere.

According to Matsuta, using audio-visual resources to support students' comprehension is advantageous since it will keep students, especially beginners, from being dissatisfied with authentic materials. Songs both contemporary and enduring will assist us in fostering a welcoming atmosphere. Use authentic resources and activities following the learning style of each student. In line with Guariento & Morley, "authentic materials should be used in accordance with students' ability and suitable tasks can be given to learners in which total understanding is not important."

Non-genuine materials may be utilized in the beginning stages, with authentic materials being included later once items about the learners' own subject areas are used. Authentic materials should be introduced while students are working with resources from their subject area, according to Jordan. R. R., notes that nonauthentic materials can be used in the early stages⁵².

Conclusion.

It is clear from reading the relevant literature that many researchers advocate the use of authentic materials in language instruction. They see the usage of these materials as an effective way to inspire students, pique their curiosity, and expose them to the language they will encounter in the real world. Additionally, since they see themselves using the language in everyday situations, genuine resources motivate students to learn a language successfully. Guariento & Morely claim that using authentic resources gives students the impression that they are learning the real language, which motivates them to acquire it.

Additionally, according to Hyland, one of the most significant benefits of employing real materials is that it improves students' motivation and influences

⁵¹ Matsuta, K. (June, 2004), Applications for Using Authentic Materials in the Second Language Classroom. Retrieved from Asia University Cele Department Web site.

⁵² Nunan, D. (1999). Second language teaching and learning. Boston: Heinle and Heinle Publishers.

their learning process. Even so, some academics are opposed to using real materials in the classroom because they think they can be too culturally biased and have difficult vocabulary and structures. This might aggravate students. Despite this unfavorable perception, numerous researchers have shown that using authentic materials when teaching ESL students outweighs the drawbacks and remains a crucial strategy that EFL teachers should use to aid their students in learning the language. Additionally, the findings of the study conducted by Baniabdelrahman demonstrate that using authentic resources is "more effective than using non-authentic materials" while teaching English to EFL learners. The latter is and undoubtedly will be the researchers' opinion that such authentic resources are crucial to the process of effective, real-world learning that must take place in every teacher's classroom.

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